

CHARACTERIZATION OF MULTI-FUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES WITH PRINTED PRESSURE SENSORS

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Keywords: *embedded sensors, functionality, structural integrity, carbon fiber, exoprosthesis*

1 Introduction

The fundamental function of a structure made of fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) is to carry structural loads. Composites that provide additional functions are known as multi-functional composites (MFC) [1, 2]. Multi-functional composites avoid redundancies that occur during the application of the traditional approach of assembling additional components to fulfill additional functional requirements [1].

Due to the fact that MFC can provide several non-structural functions such as sensing and/or actuation [2], it has become an area of intensive research [3] and plays a key role in the design of today's competitive products [4]. Since the manufacture of MFC is accompanied by challenges with both electrical component functionality and structural integrity [5], several researchers have investigated these issues.

Functionality

Using MFC, most publications indicate no problems with functionality, which can be challenged by short circuits of the sensor/actuator by carbon fiber [6, 7]. For instance, Yan and Yam [8] successfully used five piezoelectric patches embedded in a composite made of glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRP) to detect online initial damage in the host structure. Lin and Chang [9] developed a manufacturing method for MFC with built-in networks of piezoceramic sensors/actuators. Their thin flexible layers with a network of piezoceramics, known as "SMART Layers", were successfully embedded into several composites made of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP). Several works that also utilized "SMART Layers" confirmed the functionality of built-in networks [7, 10–12]. Multi-functional composites showed excellent stability and repeatability in data acquisition compared to

approaches with traditional surface bonded sensors [7].

The functionality of MFC, whose host structure is based on thermoplastics, was scientifically proven by Hufenbach et al. [4]. This working group successfully integrated sensor networks consisting of strain gauges, interconnection buses, and circuits into composites made of glass fiber reinforced polypropylene to monitor structural health.

In contrast to these works where the functionality has been demonstrated, there were also works that failed to demonstrate functionality of MFC. For instance, Etches et al. [13] could not demonstrate the functionality of their MFC. The authors embedded piezoelectric fibers into a composite made of GFRP to generate controlled deflection of the host structure. Due to problems arising from the manufacturing process, the strain output was insufficient and hence the functionality failed.

Structural integrity

Compared to the mainly homogeneous results published for functionality, the results published for structural integrity were more heterogeneous. Embedding sensors/actuators into the host structure resulted in either weakening or non-noticeable effects on the mechanical properties of MFC.

Weakening effects are due to the fact that the host structure is compromised by the presence of the embedded device [14]. The integration of sensors/actuators can cause disruptions or delaminations, and can create planes for crack propagations within the host structure [13]. Warkentin et al. [6] determined that tensile strength of composites made of CFRP with eight plies [0/90/0₂]_s and an embedded silicon chip were decreased by 15 % when using standard curing temperatures of 177° C compared to uni-functional composites (UFC). Decreases of 4 % in the average

tensile strength and in the average modulus of elasticity of MFC compared to UFC were reported by Mall and Coleman [5]. The authors tested four specimens made of CFRP with quasi isotropic $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ lay-up and two specimens with additional embedded piezoelectric lead zirconate titanate (PZT) sensors. Crawley and de Luis [15] showed that the tensile strength of GFRP laminates with embedded PZT was reduced by 20 %.

Nevertheless, some researchers also reported strategies to reduce weakening effects on MFC. Warkentin et al. [6] demonstrated that a lower curing temperature reduced the weakening effects for tensile strength. Hansen and Vizzini [14] demonstrated that the onset of damage of CFRP with embedded devices can be delayed by the application of a structural tailoring technique known as interlacing.

Conversely, several publications reported non-noticeable effects on the mechanical properties of host structures with embedded sensors/actuators. Kim et al. [16] found that the in-plane compressive and three-point bend strengths of MFC may not be necessarily reduced by embedded sensors. Furthermore, their results were independent of whether the specimens were made of thermosetting or thermoplastic matrix and whether the lay-up was unidirectional $[0]_{16}$, cross-ply $[0_4/90_4]_s$ or quasi-isotropic $[0_2/90_2/+45_2/-45_2]_s$.

The application of "SMART Layer" to the manufacture of MFC was also considered to have no influence on the structural integrity of the host structure. Qing et al. [11] embedded a "SMART Layer" into woven CFRP with twelve plies $[0_4/90_4/0_4]$. They noticed no effects on the strength of the host composite structure in three-point bending. Similar results were obtained by Su et al. [7] who embedded twelve PZT discs into woven CFRP laminates and observed no problems with structural integrity. The mechanical tests with embedded piezoelectric sensors/actuators inside CFRP performed by Lin et al. [9] also demonstrated that the structural integrity of the host composite structure was not degraded.

Fields of application

Despite the fact that MFC was intensively researched and its application has been receiving a great deal of attention [17], in fields like aerospace, automotive and shipbuilding, MFC plays no role in

the medical industry to date. This is remarkable, since the use of MFC would have great potential for medical applications.

For instance, MFC could be used to measure the interface pressure distributions in exoprostheses. Suitable structures could be composed of a host structure made of CFRP with embedded pressure sensors. Those pressure sensors normally operate on the capacitive, the piezoelectric or the piezoresistive effect. For tactile purposes however, pressure sensors that use the piezoresistive effect are dominant [20]. These sensors use either the shunt mode or the through mode that decreases the electrical resistance when being mechanically loaded.

In the field of exoprostheses the occurrence of pain, tissue breakdown and pressure ulceration at the interface between exoprostheses and residual limbs is usually attributed to a poor socket fit [18]. Therefore, orthopedists aim to measure the interface pressure distributions. Since the state of the art in measuring pressure distributions at the interface is subject to systematic errors, the application of MFC with pressure sensing functions would improve current research methods [19].

In the special case of measuring pressure distributions at the interface between residual limb and exoprosthesis, the application of printed pressure sensors would be favorable. This is due to the fact that printed pressure sensors have less thickness, better flexibility, and better cost-effectiveness when compared to traditional pressure sensors [21]. Printed piezoresistive pressure sensors usually are composed of two stacked substrates. The top of the bottom substrate is printed with interdigital electrode fingers, whereas the underside of the top substrate is printed with an insulating, elastic polymeric matrix and conductive filler material such as carbon black.

Heretofore, only the functionality of MFC with printed pressure sensors has been investigated by researchers [19], while the structural integrity has not. Hence, the objective of this study was to characterize the mechanical properties of MFC made of CFRP and printed pressure sensors.

2 Methods

In total, 75 specimens were manufactured and mechanically tested (Fig. 1). Among these specimens, two-thirds were comprised of MFC and one-third of UFC. Since the structural integrity of the host structure is considered to be independent of whether or not the embedded sensor is active [22], the required printed pressure sensors were substituted with non-functional sensor homologues. The sensor substitutes were embedded between the mid-layers of the host structure for a total of 25 specimens (MFC_I), and beneath the top layer of the host structure for another total of 25 specimens (MFC_{II}).

2.1 Manufacturing process

Whether MFC or UFC, all specimens were cut from CFRP plates that were manufactured using a handcraft laminating process in combination with a pre-designed frame to assist in sensor substitute alignment (Fig. 2). Required $\pm 45^\circ$ composite tabs were cut from handcraft laminated GFRP plates.

The components used to make the CFRP plates were epoxy resin (Epoxydharz L, R&G Faserverbundwerkstoffe GmbH, Waldenbuch, Germany), hardener (Härter EPH 161, R&G Faserverbundwerkstoffe, Waldenbuch, Germany), carbon fibers (Torayaca T 700 SC, R&G Faserverbundwerkstoffe, Waldenbuch, Germany) and, in the case of MFC, sensor substitutes. The components used to make the GFRP plates were epoxy resin and biaxial glass fibers (Silan, R&G Faserverbundwerkstoffe GmbH, Waldenbuch, Germany).

The sensor substitutes were made of 0.075 mm thick polyimide foils (Kapton HN, DuPont, Wilmington, USA) with a printed conducting path (DuPont 5028, DuPont, Wilmington, USA) whose endpoints were connected with 0.2 mm diameter enameled copper wires (KL002, Kemo Electronic GmbH, Langen, Germany). The conducting paths were produced using a semi-automatic screen printer (X1-SL, ASYS Group, Boennigheim, Germany). The connection between conducting path and lead wire was provided using conducting adhesive (PC 3601, W.C. Heraeus GmbH, Hanau, Germany). Epoxy resin was used to cover the connection to prevent short circuit with carbon fiber (Fig. 3).

Subsequent to the handcraft laminating process, the CFRP and GFRP plates were evacuated for 24 h using a desiccator, then cured for 15 h at 50° C in a furnace (SO 2032, Linn High Therm GmbH, Eschenfelden, Germany) and then stored at ambient temperature for at least one week. Thereafter, the specimens and tabs were cut to the theoretical dimensions required by the applied testing procedures using water jet cutting. The measured dimensions of finished specimens were determined using a caliper.

2.2 Mechanical testing

Mechanical properties of the specimens were determined using three different testing procedures. The testing procedures were adapted from (i) DIN standard EN ISO 527 part one [23], four [24] and five [25] to determine the tensile properties, (ii) DIN standard EN ISO 14129 [26] to determine the shear properties, and (iii) DIN standard EN ISO 14126 [27] to determine the compressive properties (Table 1). All testing procedures were performed with Z100 THW Allround-Line (Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm, Germany). Each test was run parallel (i.e. 0°) and transverse (i.e. 90°) to fiber direction except for shear testing that was run at an angle of $\pm 45^\circ$ to fiber direction.

2.2 Statistical Analysis

According to the ISO standards, the mechanical properties were determined as the mean values (\bar{v}). In detail, the following parameters were determined:

- modulus of elasticity in tension (E_t)
- tensile strength (σ_M)
- tensile strain at tensile strength (ϵ_M)
- in-plane shear modulus (G_{12})
- in-plane shear strength (τ_{12M})
- modulus of elasticity in compression (E_c)
- compressive strength (σ_{cM})
- compressive strain at compressive strength (ϵ_{cM})

Results of tested specimens that buckled or failed to reach the strain of 0.0025 were discarded. Additionally, the standard deviation of all specimens and the percent error (δ) between UFC, MFC_I and MFC_{II} were calculated using mean UFC values as reference (v_{ref}).

$$\delta = \frac{V - V_{ref}}{V_{ref}} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

3 Results

The variance of measured length and width of all specimens compared to the theoretical dimensions was less than or equal to 1.5 %. The variance of measured thickness was up to 30 % (Table 2). None of the specimens that differed from theoretical dimensions were rejected from mechanical tests. Nevertheless, the results of 22 specimens had to be discarded. Nine specimens did not reach the required strain of 0.0025, twelve specimens buckled while being compressed, and one specimen fractured during the clamping procedure. Hence, mean mechanical properties and standard deviation as well as percentage errors were calculated using the measured values for the remaining 53 tested specimens.

Mechanical properties were greater for composites using unidirectional laminates with parallel fibers, compared to either unidirectional laminates with transverse fibers or to balanced laminates whose fibers were orientated $\pm 45^\circ$ (Table 3-5). Additionally, UFC had higher mechanical properties than MFC_I or MFC_{II}. The mean modulus of elasticity in tension (E_t) of unidirectional CFRP with either parallel or transverse fibers was reduced by 17.4 % or 14.2 % due to the embedment of a sensor substitute. The mean in-plane shear modulus (G_{12}) of MFC_I and MFC_{II} were reduced by 8.2 % and 5.3 %, respectively. The mean modulus of elasticity in compression (E_c) of MFC_I and MFC_{II} were reduced by 48.4 % and 19.6 %, respectively. The strengths of the measured specimens indicated similar results. Mean tensile strength ($\bar{\sigma}_M$), mean in-plane shear strength ($\bar{\tau}_{12M}$) and mean compressive strength ($\bar{\sigma}_{cM}$) of MFC_I and MFC_{II} compared to UFC were reduced. The reduction was between 11.5 % and 52.2 %.

The failure pictures of the specimens that could be identified without additional supporting measures did not distinguish between UFC and MFC. Tested specimens with transverse fibers showed mostly transverse cracking, independently of being strained or compressed (Fig. 4). Strained specimens with parallel fibers showed fiber breakage (Fig. 5). The failure pictures of compressed unidirectional

laminates with parallel fibers and of strained balanced laminates with $\pm 45^\circ$ fibers could not be defined.

4 Discussion

The present study characterized the mechanical properties of MFC made of CFRP and printed pressure sensors using tensile, shear and compressive tests. The results indicated that MFC with embedded sensor substitutes reduces the modulus of elasticity in tension and the tensile strength of the host structures. These results were in accordance with publications that also detected weakening effects [5, 6, 15]. However, the weakening effects found in the present study were higher compared to literature.

This might be explained by the fact that, in contrast to the specimens tested in literature, the present study tested specimens with unidirectional roving. If we consider the results of shear tests that were performed like tensile tests, we can infer that using non-unidirectional specimens would demonstrate reduced weakening effects in agreement with literature. Therefore one could say that embedded sensor substitutes have greater weakening effects on unidirectional host structures compared with non-unidirectional host structures. However, there was one publication where non-noticeable effects were reported on the strength of MFC based on unidirectional laminates [16].

Another explanation for the observed greater weakening effects in the present study might be the assembly procedure utilized to construct the MFC. The procedure treated the sensor substitute like an active sensor. Hence, the sensor substitute was bonded using enameled copper wires, conducting adhesive, and epoxy resin for insulation. As a consequence of the assembly procedure the variance of measured thickness increased. In addition, some specimens were visibly compromised.

In addition to published research findings, the present study also characterized the properties of MFC under compressive loading. Based on the results one could conclude that compressive loading of MFC with embedded sensor substitutes has more negative effects than tensile loading.

5 Outlook

In a next step, the assembly procedure will be revised. The scope of the revised procedure is a significantly reduced compromising of the structural integrity of MFC. Subsequently the mechanical properties of MFC with active printed sensors that were manufactured using the revised assembly procedure will be characterized. The primary objective is the manufacture and embedding of active printed pressure sensors that can be used to measure pressure distributions at the interface between residual limbs and exoprostheses.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Mr. Mueller and Mr. Hoenig for their assistance in the handcraft laminating process as well as Mr. Kuehnrich and Mr. Koeber for their assistance in testing specimens. Funding for this research was provided by the European Social Fund (ESF) that was set up by the European Union (EU) and managed within the Free State of Saxony by the Development Bank of Saxony (SAB).

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Figures

Fig. 1. Overview of all handcraft laminated specimens that were used to determine the mechanical properties

Fig. 2. Working step of the handcraft laminating process showing impregnated carbon fibers, sensor substitutes, enameled copper wires, and the pre-designed frame to align the substitutes correctly

Fig. 3. Sensor substitutes with printed conducting paths that were insulated with epoxy resin

Fig. 4. Failure pictures of specimens with transverse fiber orientation showing transverse cracking as a result of compression (a) or strain (b)

Fig. 5. Failure pictures of specimens with parallel fiber orientation showing fiber breakage as a result of strain

Tables

Table 1. Testing parameters of testing procedures

	tensile test		shear test	compression test	
	parallel	transverse	shear	parallel	transverse
lay-up	[0 ₆]	[90 ₁₂]	[+45/-45] ₆	[0 ₁₂]	[90 ₁₂]
theoretical UFC dimension [mm]	250 x 15 x 0.94	250 x 25 x 1.87	250 x 25 x 1.87	110 x 10 x 1.87	110 x 10 x 1.87
theoretical MFC dimension [mm]	250 x 15 x 1.06	250 x 25 x 2.00	250 x 25 x 2.00	110 x 10 x 2.00	110 x 10 x 2.00
theoretical tab dimension [mm]	50 x 15 x 1.02	50 x 15 x 1.02	50 x 15 x 1.02	50 x 15 x 1.02	50 x 15 x 1.02
testing speed [mm·min⁻¹]	2	2	2	1	1
grip/tool	hydraulic	hydraulic	hydraulic	ITTRI [28]	ITTRI [28]
preload	10 N	10 N	10 N	0.1 MPa	0.1 MPa
strain measurement (parallel)	laserXtens	laserXtens	laserXtens	strain gauge	two strain gauges
strain measurement (transverse)	strain gauge	strain gauge	laserXtens	strain gauge	-

Table 2. Measured dimensions and percentage error (δ) of all specimens compared to theoretical dimensions

			length (mm)	width (mm)	δ width (%)	thickness (mm)	δ thickness (%)
tensile test	parallel	UFC	250	14.91 ± 0.02	-0.6	0.80 ± 0.04	-14.9
		MFC _I	250	14.78 ± 0.05	-1.5	0.87 ± 0.01	-17.9
		MFC _{II}	250	14.82 ± 0.02	-1.2	0.92 ± 0.04	-13.2
	transverse	UFC	250	25.05 ± 0.04	0.2	1.79 ± 0.11	-4.3
		MFC _I	250	24.92 ± 0.03	-0.3	2.06 ± 0.04	3.0
		MFC _{II}	250	24.92 ± 0.06	-0.3	2.05 ± 0.09	2.5
shear test	shear	UFC	250	25.01 ± 0.02	0.0	1.93 ± 0.08	3.2
		MFC _I	250	24.99 ± 0.02	0.0	2.20 ± 0.19	10.0
		MFC _{II}	250	24.95 ± 0.01	-0.2	2.41 ± 0.24	20.5
compression test	parallel	UFC	110	9.98 ± 0.01	-0.2	1.54 ± 0.08	-17.6
		MFC _I	110	9.96 ± 0.04	-0.4	2.60 ± 0.05	30.0
		MFC _{II}	110	9.94 ± 0.02	-0.6	1.71 ± 0.15	-14.5
	transverse	UFC	110	9.99 ± 0.02	-0.1	1.60 ± 0.06	-14.4
		MFC _I	110	9.96 ± 0.03	-0.4	2.41 ± 0.28	20.5
		MFC _{II}	110	9.89 ± 0.04	-1.1	2.09 ± 0.28	4.5

Table 3. Summary of mean tensile properties

	n	E_t (GPa)	$\bar{\sigma}_M$ (MPa)	$\bar{\epsilon}_M$ (%)
UFC 0°	5	117.1 ± 7.1	1716 ± 76	1.4 ± 0.1
MFC _I 0°	5	103.4 ± 2.3	1243 ± 69	2.6 ± 1.6
MFC _{II} 0°	5	96.7 ± 7.2	1120 ± 122	2.3 ± 0.8
UFC 90°	3	7.3 ± 0.2	23 ± 1	0.2 ± 0.1
MFC _I 90°	4	6.4 ± 0.3	19 ± 2	0.2 ± 0.0
MFC _{II} 90°	4	6.3 ± 0.1	19 ± 1	0.2 ± 0.1

Note. n indicates the number of valid tests, E_t indicates the mean modulus of elasticity in tension, $\bar{\sigma}_M$ indicates the mean tensile strength and $\bar{\epsilon}_M$ indicates the mean tensile strain at tensile strength

Table 4. Summary of mean shear properties

	n	G₁₂ (GPa)	$\bar{\tau}_{12M}$ (MPa)
UFC ±45°	5	3.1 ± 0.1	51 ± 1
MFC _I ±45°	5	2.9 ± 0.3	45 ± 2
MFC _{II} ±45°	5	3.0 ± 0.2	42 ± 3

Note. n indicates the number of valid tests, G₁₂ indicates the mean in-plane shear modulus and $\bar{\tau}_{12M}$ indicates the mean in-plane shear strength

Table 5. Summary of mean compressive properties

	n	E_c (GPa)	$\bar{\sigma}_{cM}$ (MPa)	$\bar{\epsilon}_{cM}$ (%)
UFC 0°	0	-	-	-
MFC _I 0°	0	-	-	-
MFC _{II} 0°	2	85.3 ± 20.4	309 ± 21	0.4 ± 0.1
UFC 90°	4	10.0 ± 3.1	94 ± 9	1.3 ± 0.3
MFC _I 90°	3	5.2 ± 1.3	46 ± 7	1.0 ± 0.0
MFC _{II} 90°	2	8.0 ± 4.6	45 ± 13	0.7 ± 0.2

Note. n indicates the number of valid tests, E_c indicates the mean modulus of elasticity in compression, $\bar{\sigma}_{cM}$ indicates the mean compressive strength and $\bar{\epsilon}_{cM}$ indicates the mean compressive strain at compressive strength